

2ND INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON BIOSCIENCES RESEARCH (ICBR) – OWERRI 2016

Biosciences Research Support Foundation

in collaboration with

Hezekiah University, Umudi, Imo State, Nigeria

PROGRAM OF EVENTS

November 24, 2016

Arrival and Registration

November 25, 2016

- 8:00 – 10:00 Registration continues
10:00 – 10:15 Introduction of MC, Chief host, BRSF President and Scientific Advisers, Keynote and Invited Speakers
10:15 – 10:30 Welcome address by the President, BRSF
- Keynote Speakers
10:30 – 11:00 **Prof. Asokan Chinnasamy:** *Development of Therapeutic and Diagnostic Molecules by rDNA and Hybridoma Technology*
11:00 – 11:30 **Prof. Ifeoma M. Ezeonu:** *The Use of Molecular Techniques in Microbial diagnostics*
11:30 – 12:00 **Prof. Emeka Iweala:** *Molecular Biology: Avenue to Understanding and Controlling Cancer*
- Invited Speakers (Plenary Session I)
12:00 – 12:30 **Dr. Eman A. Alam:** *Pharmacological studies on the Qurani plants' mixture (a new pharmaceutical product)*
12:30 – 13:00 **Dr. Mohd A. Ansari:** *Biochemical iodine deficiency - a field based longitudinal study in selected schools of Aligarh, India*
13:00 – 14:00 Other speakers 20 mins each
14:00 – 15:00 Break/Lunch
15:00 – 17:30 Plenary Session II

November 26, 2016

- 8:00 – 9:00 Registration Continues
9:00 – 13:00 Plenary Session III
13:00 – 14:00 Break/Lunch
14:00 – 17:00 Plenary Session IV
17:00 – 17:20 Interaction of audience with BRSF
17:20 – 17:30 Closing remarks by the PRO of Hezekiah University
17:30 – 18:00 Award of certificates to participants

November 27, 2016

Departure